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Nuancing Psychological Research with Complexity: The Case of Ecological Dynamics and Embodied Cognition

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Psychological science is often hampered by the fact that mind and behavior are exceedingly complex subjects. There are many moving parts, and many interactions between these, which elicits a categorical shift in the nature of its variables. This demands a strong theoretic and pre-theoretic foundation to order and interpret results. Yet, especially the meta-theoretic foundation has been unduly neglected. This involves scrutinizing assumptions about the nature of the world implicit in theories, called *metaphysics*. We position complexity science as delivering effective methods by which to do this. Our analysis exposes meta-theoretic assumptions by asking whether a theory assumes that psychological phenomena 1) are the product of a complex system, 2) behave as a complex system, and 3) should be investigated as a complex system. We predict that this analysis will expose that theories often differ in their (meta-theoretic) metaphysical assumptions of complexity, as opposed to their explicit theoretic postulates. It therefore nuances psychological theories by exposing the underlying causes of differences in theories, furthering the productivity of discussions. We first present this analysis and consequently turn it towards a case study, comparing two frameworks which share but also differ in meta-theoretic and theoretic postulates. This ambivalent proximity allows to demonstrate the strengths of the complexity perspective as an incisive tool for investigating conflicting positions.

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Introduction

Psychological science is “the study of the mind and behavior” (APA Dictionary, n.d.; see also e.g., Rooney & Evans, 2019), an exceedingly *complex* subject matter. Yet, much psychological research fails to give this fact very much attention. In fact, considerable psychological research is in conflict with mind and behavior’s inherent complexity. The tide may be turning though; especially in the wake of discussions around psychological science’s replication crisis, the topic of complexity has increasingly surfaced (e.g., Eronen & Bringmann, 2025; Gernigon et al., 2024; Sanbonmatsu & Johnston, 2019; Van Der Maas, 2024). We expand on this recent surge in work, presenting the complexity view as a valuable perspective for drawing out implicitly held theoretical assumptions. Often, theories or frameworks differ in their explicit positions not because of theoretic, but rather because of meta-theoretic differences. Here, a discussion of theoretic differences would not be fruitful, and to push such discussions to more fruitful territory, a tool for navigating the metaphysical distinctions is necessary. Complexity is such an incisive tool for exposing implicit commitments. In this paper, we first argue that a common theme driving meta-theoretic differences is the implicit commitment to complexity, and then produce an analysis of metaphysical differences. Consequently, we provide an example of this by treating two frameworks that have embraced complexity in varying ways, Embodied Cognition and Ecological Dynamics. Their commonalities and conflicts demonstrate complexity’s potential as an instrument to scrutinize positions.

To this aim, we will begin by first looking at the role of meta-theoretic assumptions in shaping psychological research, and how it relates to the harmful overreliance on empirical, as opposed to theoretical work. This leads us to a brief overview of complexity. Consequently, we apply complexity as a guide to navigating metaphysical questions. We outline the metaphysical domain in three *levels of analysis*, that span from more general assumptions about what exists in the world to more specific assumptions about how this should be investigated. This is followed by an introduction of our two example approaches, embodied cognition and ecological dynamics. We extract commonalities and differences between these approaches using the levels of

analysis previously explained. We therefore have two central aims: 1) position complexity as a guiding perspective for nuancing psychological theories, and 2) apply it to nuance the discussion between ecological dynamics and embodied cognition. To clarify, this analysis does not intend to describe the differences between complexity-based psychological research and standard psychology (for such work, see e.g., Araújo et al., 2019; Den Hartigh et al., 2017; Favela, 2020).

As the point of departure for this argumentation, and as conceptual background for our discussion, we motivate that any science, but psychological science especially, must have a strong theoretical foundation. Psychology's lack of theoretical rigor has been frequently lamented (e.g., Eronen & Bringmann, 2021; Fiedler, 2017; Gigerenzer, 2010; Lykken, 1991; Meehl, 1967). To depict this, Forscher (1963) uses the vignette of a brickyard. In this analogy, science is the enterprise of building edifices (explanations and laws) which the builders (scientists) construct. The goal of the builders is to skillfully assemble bricks (empirical findings) to build a strong and durable building. In earlier times, the builders produced their own bricks, changing material and form depending on the purpose. Yet, with increasing investment, they found that they could train brickmakers who could focus solely on producing bricks, while the builders could even more quickly build edifices. This was a productive decision and building was quicker than ever, yet in an unforeseen turn, the brickmakers became obsessed with brickmaking, no longer producing specific bricks for specific purposes, but rather focusing on producing a high number of bricks. They argued: "if enough bricks were available, the builders would be able to select what was necessary and still continue to construct edifices." (Forscher, 1963, p. 339). With time, the land became flooded with bricks, the job of builder became a rarity, and the shapes and materials of the bricks were not governed by the needs of the edifice, but by changing trends and fashions from other brickmakers. In fact, with time, true edifices disappeared, as the distinction between a pile of bricks and an edifice dissolved (Forscher, 1963). 'Chaos in the brickyard' is a decidedly severe depiction of past and current norms in psychological science, yet it touches on a real systematic neglect of theoretical aspects of the scientific enterprise, which integrate and give meaning to the wealth of empirical findings. Modern psychological research often neglects the

'bigger picture' and often prefers to proceed one step – one empirical finding – at a time, presuming that this collection of empirical evidence will one day by itself uncover a sufficiently complete picture of mind and behavior.

Metaphysics

A critically neglected fact undermining this undirected collection of empirical evidence is that even ostensibly objective, 'untainted' empirical findings are not free from theoretical consideration. The objects of investigation in psychological science are often intangible. Therefore, theories cannot be sufficiently constrained to produce definitive, objective, facts (Eronen & Bringmann, 2021; McGann & Speelman, 2020). In other words, psychological phenomena are *underdetermined*; One set of empirical findings can be interpreted in multiple ways, a theory or hypothesis cannot be definitively evidenced or refuted based on data alone (Stanford, 2009). The distance between theory and data is too large to allow excluding all possible alternative explanations, and therefore for absolute insights. Therefore, whether the results of an experiment speak in favor of one theory or another depends on the interpretation of data, an act which taints ostensibly objective data with theoretical assumptions (for an example of this, see the commentary on a recent failed replication; Buckwalter & Friedman, 2024).

The interpretive structure one invariably uses to understand data derives from one's *metaphysics*. Metaphysics are one's assumptions about what constitutes the world. These include assumptions about what constitutes knowledge (epistemology), claims about what exists in the world (ontology), and one's picture of the universe as a whole (cosmology; Henriques, 2019; see also Crotty, 2020; van Zomeren, 2024; Slife & Williams, 1995). They are meta-theoretic, meaning they underlie more specific, elaborate theoretical considerations. Psychological researchers often delegate heady philosophical concepts like ontology or epistemology to philosophers, eschewing these metaphysical questions for the more tangible domains of hypothesis and data (Eronen & Bringmann, 2021; Henriques, 2019; Slife & Williams, 1995). Yet, the neglect of such metaphysics ignores the underdetermined nature of empirical data in psychology. One's metaphysics will always sneak into the interpretation of data.

This is made evident by considering how one's choice in methods are driven by metaphysical assumptions. One chooses methods that produce the type of data which the metaphysical position requires. If one has a realist metaphysical position, in which there is a publicly accessible, existing reality beyond the researcher, the methods one chooses must be resistant to the influence of the investigator, by using e.g., double-blinding. This is very different if one assumes that all reality is only created or idealized relative to the investigator, in which one would make explicit one's private view and interpretation in e.g., an interview study (Guba & Lincoln, 1994).

Metaphysical assumptions therefore play a central role in the entire scientific enterprise. Yet, when theories are compared, one most often 'looks down' and compares data, such as in critical inference testing, where contrasting hypotheses are derived from two theories to decide the better theory (Bouchard, 2009; Platt, 1964). Yet, it is rarely recommended to look up, to identify the metaphysical commitments underlying the theories, which could allow to tease them apart. Indeed, two theories that make fundamentally different assumptions about what exists in the world, or how nature works, can hardly be pitted against one another. They may be in conflict and yet both be plausible (cf. Derksen & Morawski, 2022; Favela & Chemero, 2023).

We hope to have now made evident the critical detriment of ignoring the meta-theoretic foundation, and the central importance of it in the scientific endeavor. In this paper, we present complexity as a valuable guiding perspective for navigating this metaphysical territory. Next, we describe the concept of complexity and its relation to scientific thinking. As complexity is not a psychological framework, and rather a discipline-spanning perspective (Krakauer, 2024), this presentation will necessarily be domain-general. Indeed, one of complexity's strengths is that it relies on system-general (i.e., universal), physical principles.

Complexity

Complexity science is a field concerned with understanding how simple entities (whether particles, ants, or neurons) become organized without the help of a central controller to exhibit novel, often intelligent, behaviors (Mitchell, 2011). Complex systems consist of many reciprocally interacting components with typically many degrees of freedom and exhibiting some sort of unity or

coordination, termed *self-organization* (Erdi, 2008; Zuchowski, 2012)¹. This basic assumption leads to a set of tools, techniques, and approaches which differ strongly from the predominant modus operandi in sciences (whether biological, economic, behavioral, political; Mainzer, 2007; von Bertalanffy, 1968). In contrast to a complex system, a simple system may consist of many components, but these are not in reciprocal interaction with each other². The predominant modus operandi across the sciences is the mechanistic view, which assumes that all nature consists of simple systems, and therefore can be explained by reducing them to their known parts and understanding these in isolation (Capra & Luisi, 2014).

Two features which characterize complex systems are *emergence* and *non-linearity*. Emergence describes the tendency for a system to exhibit patterns at the macroscopic level that are not immediately discernible from its components. In other words, that the whole is more than the sum of its parts (Anderson, 1972). Such patterns emerge from the interactions between the components that make up a system. These components begin to self-organize, acting as a whole. The causes of complex systems' behavior, can be traced, not to the attributes of single components, but rather to the macroscopic patterns which a vast multiplication of these interactions produces. Systems such as this, where the drivers of behavior can be traced to the interactions between components, as opposed to the attributes of the components themselves, are called *interaction-dominant* (Van Orden et al., 2003). To illustrate, a snowflake's intricate patterns originate from interactions between single ice particles and are hardly discernible from the attributes of single particles.

¹ There is no consensus on the exact meaning of the term complexity (Gell-Mann, 2002), especially across disciplines where the meaning ranges vastly (giving rise to an "interdisciplinary tower of babel"; Scott, 1991). The explication we provide here should be satisfactory and depict the essential parts relevant for the current discussion.

² There is an important misunderstanding to avoid the common misconception between simple and easy. Simple systems can be extraordinarily complicated and hard to understand, such as in the case of a rocket. Therefore, the term complex refers only to the nature of the components and their interactions and makes no statement to the sophistication of their explanations. See Hartigh et al. (2017) for further discussion.

The second feature of complex systems is that of non-linearity. As described above, complex systems involve reciprocal feedback loops, meaning that any one component influences, but is also influenced by, another given component. Such circular causation, or *recursiveness*, leads the system's macroscopic behavior to fall into self-reinforcing or self-inhibiting feedback loops. Furthering the intricacy, complex systems are *multi-level*; there are many scales across which a system self-organizes (particles, cells, muscles, etc.). Feedback loops take place within and across these scales. As a result of these many feedback loops, a change in one part of the system can lead to over- or under-proportionate changes in the system's subsequent functioning. This translates, in statistical terms, to non-linearity because there are no linear relations between causes and effects. Typically, acknowledging the non-linearity of natural phenomena is accompanied by rejecting mechanistic explanations, which aim to isolate single causes of phenomena. Rather, a complexity perspective posits that multiple causes lead to multiple effects which are causes for the same effects, dissolving the distinction between causes and effects (Capra & Luisi, 2014; Machamer et al., 2000).

In science, the complexity perspective therefore tends to emphasize different aspects of phenomena than the standard, non-complexity, approaches. Standard approaches often implicitly rely on the assumption that a system is best understood by looking to its components (cf. description of *decomposition*, below). For example, traditional linear regression or ANOVA-based methods typically isolate variables under the assumption of independence (that phenomena are caused by single, isolated components) and linear causality (that increases in one variable lead to proportionate effects in another). While these may include interaction terms, these are usually isolated few (most often two) variables at few timepoints. They thereby ignore the recursive, multilevel, and nonlinear interdependencies that characterize complex systems.

On the other hand, complexity approaches argue that this approach fails to capture the innumerable reciprocal recurrences between these individual components and the many others that impinge on them and their interaction. Instead, based on the assumption of interaction-dominance, it looks at system-level attributes, which allow to depict or capture the full scale of interactions (Mitchell, 2009). Key concepts here are attractors' dynamics (states the system

revisits often and which tend to be local minima), constraints (links among components which reduces system's degrees of freedom), control parameters (outside influences which force state changes in a system), and order parameters (one of a small number of variables that summarize a system's macroscopic pattern; Haken, 1977; Kelso, 1995). These concepts are used to understand how the system changes as a whole, what constrains a system's behavior, how it is coupled to other systems, but not to understand the components that make up a system.

In psychological research, the complexity perspective, despite certainly not being the predominant approach, can be found in various fields. In neuroscience, approaches like dynamical field theory view neurocognitive processes as emerging from dynamic interactions between different neural fields (Schöner, 2009). In developmental psychology, Esther Thelen and colleagues' dynamic systems theory conceptualizes cognition arises from self-organizing interactions among multiple systems (neurological, motor, perceptual, environmental), it develops through movement and interaction with the environment (Thelen et al., 2001). In social and personality psychology, the self is viewed more as an attractor state emerging from self-organization of individual experiences (Vallacher et al., 2002; Vallacher & Nowak, 1994). In cognitive science, cognitive processing is not isolated to the skull but rather extends into and beyond the body (cf. below; Engel et al., 2013; Rowlands, 2010). Also the statistics which are applied differ: Statistical techniques, such as fractal analysis focus on the variability of a system, a marker of its integration and coordination (Diniz et al., 2011; Riley & Van Orden, 2005; Stephen & Dixon, 2011) or network approaches, which aim to understand the structure of a system, whether neurological, psychopathological, sociological, or other (Bassett & Sporns, 2017; Borsboom & Cramer, 2013; Ramos et al., 2018; Watts, 2004).

The differences between complexity science and standard science are exceedingly fundamental to indeed constitute different metaphysical commitments. Assumptions of complex or simple systems drastically change how one proceeds to gain insights into the system. Therefore, as we show next, it may be a fruitful candidate to guide discussions about metaphysical commitments in various theories.

Figure 1

Three levels to interrogate metaphysical assumptions

Note. The term “Standard Psychology” intends to simply depict the default or typical assumptions implicit in psychological research (cf. Shapiro, 2019; Sulik et al., 2025)

Complexity as a Guide to Metaphysics

Psychological research is especially reliant on interpretative structures, which spring directly from a researcher’s metaphysical commitments. A neglect of metaphysical questions is therefore detrimental. To assess these metaphysical beliefs, we argue, it is useful to use complexity as a guide. Delivered by the complexity approach explained above are a number of metaphysical commitments. Based on these, we parse the metaphysical domain into three levels of analysis or steps³: 1) complex vs. simple, 2) monism vs. dualism, and 3) system-level vs. decomposition (see Fig. 1). Each level

³ One may parse these levels of analysis differently, and in fact the categories within these levels are also not strict. For example, Henriques (2019) takes as part of metaphysical assumptions the ontology and cosmology, while Heylighen et al. (2007) describes ontological and metaphysical assumptions as separate. We choose these levels because they capture three central pieces of the complexity versus simplicity debate, but do not believe this to be a definitive or comprehensive list of metaphysical considerations.

serves to interrogate one's metaphysical beliefs and their relation to theory and methodology. By framing these as steps, in which one leads to the next, it allows to evince the sequence of commitments and carve out conceptual distinctions. We use these questions about complexity across different levels of analysis to afterwards nuance the positions of embodied cognition and ecological dynamics.

The first step asks, are psychological phenomena the product of a complex system like other natural phenomena? It relates to the origin of psychological phenomena, with the positions of a *simple* or *complex* system. It is largely accepted that psychological phenomena – indeed all of life – are the product of complex systems (e.g., Dyson, 1999; Kauffman, 1993; Luisi, 2016; Nicolis & Prigogine, 1977; Walker & Davies, 2013). This means that these phenomena are emergent and can be traced to the mechanisms of self-organization. On the position of simple, one may argue that the mind and behavior arose fully independently from life. For example, one may take the position that humans are the product of divine intervention, and therefore not the product of a complex system. Such a position is unlikely to be accepted in academic discourse. A more common position, arguably the default in psychological research, is to be inexplicit on this point (Van Der Maas, 2024).

The second step asks, are psychological phenomena the same or different from other natural phenomena? It relates to the attributes of psychological phenomena, where one can take the positions *dualism* and *monism*. Dualism states that psychological phenomena are fundamentally different in kind from other natural phenomena. Dualism can be traced to Descartes' dualism in which the mind and body are seen as separate. A modern, scientifically-digestible, version of dualism entails that psychological phenomena are unlike other things which exist in nature (Wilson & Golonka, 2013). For example, a common analogy in the dualist tradition is that the brain works like a computer, with different modules like memory storage, the functions of which are to perform computations (Brette, 2022; Fodor, 1983). Computers are unlike other natural phenomena, and e.g., modularity exists rarely in nature. A corollary of the computer metaphor is the "sandwich model" of the brain (Hurley, 2001), in which there are clearly distinguished stages of input (perception), processing (thinking), and output (action). This process is

also dualist, because it proposes the brain works in linear, sequential steps, in violation of principles of emergence and self-organization. In contrast to this dualism, monism posits that psychological phenomena are like any other existing phenomena. Here, psychological phenomena are conceptualized as emerging from the numerous reciprocal interactions between components, resisting all informative decomposition into stages.

If one views this step in relation to the previous, it is likely that most who profess a commitment to complex, are likely to ascribe to monism. Yet, one may also argue that, despite psychological phenomena being the product of a complex system, they nonetheless exhibit the attributes of a simple system. This is arguably the default position across standard psychology, where it may be acknowledged that surely the brain and body are the product of complex systems, yet that the brain works unlike anything else found in nature and therefore has fundamentally different attributes than other natural phenomena. Indeed, the computer metaphor is among the strongest shared belief among psychologists and cognitive scientists (Sulik et al., 2025). This tension between the dualist position of digital and symbolic cognition and accepted truisms about the origin of cognition being a complex system, for example, has led to some postulating a “biological leap” forward (Berwick & Chomsky, 2017, p. 3), a genetic mutation enabling a (dualist) symbolic cognition.

The third step asks, should the complexity of psychological phenomena be captured in its theories? It relates to research strategies, where one can perform *decomposition* or *systems-level* research. Research strategies describe how to go about acquiring useful knowledge. On the one hand, decomposition involves understanding a phenomenon by identifying the features of its components (Bechtel & Richardson, 2010). This stems from the more general epistemology of *reductionism*, which postulates that once one has understood the components of a system, one can sum these parts to understand the system as a whole. Decomposition as a research strategy aims to explain a phenomenon by describing its components. This research strategy is visible in typical practices. In theories, one can see decomposition in boxes-and-arrows type theories (Pessoa, 2017), where the causes of a phenomenon are reduced to a limited number of boxes with typically uni-directional influences (arrows) between them. Decomposition also underlies the typical practices in laboratory

work, in which typically a single variable is manipulated while all others are controlled. This is based on the assumption that interactions are negligible, and the valuable insights are to be found in the attributes of components. Therefore, the influence of that single variable is attempted to be perfectly isolated by removing all other factors. Individual variability or contextual factors are deemed as noise and 'averaged out'.

Decomposition research has, for this reason, been derisively-termed 'button-pressing' research. As an example, take the artificial context of a study investigating referees' offside decision-making. These refs were given a schematic of a 2-dimensional bird's eye view of a football pitch in which icons of attackers and defenders, sized approximately 7x21 pixels each, moved at 9 frames per second. At a time when a possibly-offside pass is played, referees are given 10 seconds to respond using one of four buttons (Gillis et al., 2008). It is evident that the context and behavior in this experiment is very dissimilar the actual behavior under investigation. The referees are sat as opposed to moving, the visual information is 2-dimensional and static, and there are artificial time constraints. Under the assumption of a simple system, this dissimilarity is not a problem, as decomposition research assumes that the interactions between the body, the perceptual information, and time constraints are negligible noise obscuring the actual signal, in this case the referee's decision. This conflicts with the assumptions from complexity science and the emergent nature of phenomena. The referee's decision cannot be traced to a single process, but rather emerges from the referee's many internal attributes and external contextual factors (cf. Kuhbandner & Mayrhofer, 2025).

Systems-level strategies, on the other hand, take seriously the assumption that one cannot understand a system by looking to its parts. This is reflected in theories that do not take the form of components (boxes) connected by uni-directional causes (arrows), but rather networks or state space trajectories (Guastello et al., 2008). Here, variables are used which depict the system's behavior as a whole, avoiding the isolation of components and acknowledging the interaction-dominance of a system. These can take the form of holistic performance trajectories (e.g., Verbeek et al., 2025) or the mapping of a network of variables (e.g., Neumann et al., 2024). Thereby, variability is viewed as a signal, as opposed to noise, of important processes.

If one views this third step in relation to the previous, one position may be that one applies a decomposition research strategy despite having previous commitments to complexity and monism. Even when assuming that the origins of psychological phenomena are a complex system (and that they therefore share attributes of other natural phenomena) they should nonetheless be (cautiously) investigated using reductionist methods (e.g., Heuer, 1988). This may be motivated by e.g., the desire to make predictions based on single variables for practitioners or intervention design. Similarly, one may want to draw conclusions from limited information, when one only has access to single variables. It is certainly justified to be interested in such single variables. Yet this must be in line with the type of knowledge one is interested in gaining about a phenomenon. In how far does knowledge about the components of a system constitute an understanding of the system itself? In one comparison of non-linear & complexity-based versus linear & reductionist models, the complexity & non-linear models outperformed simple & linear approaches, explaining more variance by a factor of 2:1 (Guastello, 2013).

Summarizing these steps, the insights from complexity science lead to three levels of analysis which build on each other. Researchers can consider whether their theory (or they themselves) assume that the origin of psychological phenomena are a complex system, whether their theory assumes that psychological phenomena behave as complex systems, and lastly whether the theory decomposes psychological phenomena or whether it assumes that insights about components constitute important insights about the system's behavior. Together, these may allow to scrutinize the implicit assumptions. It may also be valuable to consider what justifies specific decisions, such as taking a dualist stance despite assuming the origin of psychological phenomena to be complexity. Furthermore, it may also serve to pinpoint more productive differences in theories. As demonstrated in the following section.

The Case of Ecological Dynamics and Embodied Cognition

We can now turn to applying this analysis. Across the steps outlined above, complexity can be addressed in very different ways, and theories can differ in their commitment to these. In fact, we focus on two approaches that both embrace complexity to some degree. Yet they are also quite different, and applying the analysis above shows that they occupy different profiles, especially

on the final step of the three mentioned above. Guided by the previous section's insights on complexity across levels of analysis, we can compare these approaches and tease out novel points of discussion. Before proceeding, we shortly introduce the overarching category of 4E cognition, which relates to both approaches (Heras-Escribano, 2023).

4E cognition states that psychological processes should be viewed as embedded (cognition is situation-dependent), embodied (the body plays an important role in cognition), enactive (cognition arises from interaction with the environment), and extended (cognition involves the environment; Newen et al., 2018). Within this more overarching category of 4E cognition, there are varying positions that often disagree (Gentsch et al., 2016). Yet, roughly joining the various research programs is the departure from common assumptions in the standard approach: 4E programs share the common postulate that the body and situation are more important to understanding psychological processes than previously believed (Shapiro, 2019). Some core themes which resurface throughout these literatures are an emphasis on methodologies which reflect real-time situated action, the importance of viewing cognitive functioning in the context of what serves action, theories and models that reject sequential, uni-directional cognitive functioning, and a consideration of the time-component in explaining psychological processes (see Casper & Artese, 2023).

Embodied Cognition

The embodied cognition approach can be situated between the standard approach and ecological dynamics, as it rejects many of the assumptions and corresponding practices of said standard approach, yet is less radical than ecological dynamics in this. The term 'embodied cognition' has been applied to exceedingly diverse fields of study (Gentsch et al., 2016; Wilson, 2002) ranging from mirror neurons, to common coding approaches, and mental representations. For current purposes, we use the term embodied cognition to refer to a moderate embodied cognition approach⁴ which retains many of the tenets of 4E cognition but whose theories nonetheless find considerable alignment with standard psychology (cf. Goldman, 2012). Perhaps most

⁴ We acknowledge that some work called 'embodied cognition' aligns more with ecological dynamics (e.g., Chemero, 2013).

centrally, embodied cognition rejects the standard approach's view of the brain as a central controller. Instead, it emphasizes the importance of the body and action as being constitutive of psychological processes (Friedrich et al., 2025). This relates to complexity because embodied cognition replaces the simple linear causal chains (cf. boxes-and-arrows, above) with a reciprocal, bi-directional informational exchange between brain, body, and environment.

Take, for example, *perceptual symbol systems* (Barsalou, 1999, 2008) and the related *situated action cycle* (Barsalou, 2009, 2020) account of mental representations. Perceptual symbol systems argues that mental representations, even of abstract concepts, involve simulations of sensorimotor states. It argues that so-called simulators are the equivalents of concepts. They house fragments of perceptions related to a specific concept that are recruited when necessary to represent said concept. The related situated action cycle embeds this into in-the-moment representation of concepts and cognition generally, in a cycle consisting of five phases. It states that 1) individuals perceive entities (e.g., an object) in the environment and 2) assess its relevance (e.g., to the individual's goals, values,). This gives rise to 3) affect, followed by 4) action, and 5) an outcome which feeds back into the first phase, 1) perceiving entities in the environment. This theory contrasts with standard approaches for its acknowledgement of the body in cognition. It rejects the dualist notion of the brain as a central controller, positing online and offline sensorimotor information as a central component. It also replaces uni-directional causes with bi-directional and reciprocal relations between various aspects of a process, much more in line with complexity approaches according to which uni-directional causal relations are rare. The authors describe that "phases may be smeared across each other in time and/or omitted. Also, various loops and alternative relations between phases may emerge." (Barsalou, 2020, p. 3). Nonetheless, the phenomenon under investigation is understood by decomposing it into separate phases, which prevents it from fully aligning with a systems-level research strategy (see Fig. 1).

In methodology, embodied cognition research emphasizes the importance of research designs which depart from button-pressing psychology. Embodied cognition typically aims to produce research designs which incorporate more naturalistic movement (Maselli et al., 2023). Such designs

may have life-sized depictions of game scenes from the normal referee perspective, referees moving themselves, with short time constraints, and responding by raising a flag, instead of a button press (e.g., Luis del Campo et al., 2018). Thus, despite aiming to isolate the behavior of a single dependent variable, in the planning of an experiment it is acknowledged that such interactions between components are influential. Therefore, in spite of its alignment with complexity in levels one and two, its research strategy tends toward decomposition as it isolates components of the system and localizes functions to regions. For example, when identifying the seat of a mental representation by its location in a sensorimotor area (Harpaintner et al., 2020; Hauk et al., 2004).

Ecological Dynamics

Ecological dynamics argues that underlying the standard approach there is the, misleading, belief that environmental information is too ambiguous or impoverished to be meaningful (Araújo et al., 2006). It rejects the belief that sensory stimuli – like the activation of rods and cones – must be internally enriched using internal mental constructs such as mental representations or inference engines as often argued in standard approaches (e.g., Marr, 1982). Instead, it proposes that the environment offers rich, structured information in itself (referred to as ecological information), which presents action opportunities without further, internal, transformation. In other words, the patterns of light, in the case of vision, that differ across surfaces and objects, are detected directly by the perceptual visual system environment as ‘action-on-able’, and thus meaningful, without the need for internal mediators. One example is optic flow, a case in which there is a lawful change of the visual field as an observer moves, where some affordances persist and others dissolve (Gibson, 1966, 1979; Turvey, 2007). In dynamic situations, such as a scene on a football pitch, the interactions between variant (e.g., a moving adversary) and invariant features (e.g., the pitch) provides all necessary information to act adaptively, if the intention is to e.g., dribble past the adversary.

Ecological dynamics emphasizes an agent’s (for the present purposes a human’s) inseparability with the environment. The controller of behavior and the locus of mind is not viewed as being centralized to the brain or body, but rather that behavior emerges from a body acting in a situation, rejecting the need for a

central controller (Araújo et al., 2020, 2025; Davids et al., 2008). In fact, the approach rejects the value of isolating variables wholesale, as this would risk misrepresenting the causes of an interaction-dominant phenomenon. Instead, it emphasizes behavior as emerging from the individual-environment system (Araújo et al., 2025). Therefore, in contrast to standard psychology (and embodied cognition), which takes the individual as the primary unit of analysis, it takes the system made up of individual and environment as the subject of study (Seifert et al., 2016). This aligns with a categorically different approach to psychology, with a long although peripheric tradition in which the context is taken as a necessary constituent of psychological explanation (Barker, 1975; Barker & Wright, 1971; Brunswik, 1952, 1956; Gibson, 1966, 1979; Lewin, 1936). Such work carries distinct constructs and foci which we will shortly introduce here (for more comprehensive introductions to ecological dynamics see Araújo et al., 2025; Davids et al., 2013; Segundo-Ortin & Raja, 2024)

The variables of interest in ecological dynamics are not based on internal processes as in the standard approach or embodied cognition. How best then, to investigate the inseparable system composed of agent and environment? It is assumed that behavior is directed by *constraints* and *affordances*. Constraints limit the number of available degrees of freedom of the agent-environment system, and consequently shape its possible states. They are organized into three categories, those of the environment, of the agent, and of the task (Newell, 1986). Affordances, on the other hand, are possibilities for action offered by the environment in relation to the agent's capabilities in a given situation. They are considered to constrain and sometimes solicit behavior, and it is the individual who realizes them (or not). Thus, in line with complexity's rejection of mechanistic explanation, affordances do not cause action, they constrain it. When engaging with an affordance, an individual's behavior is the result of continuously coupled perception and action in a given context. When individuals act in their environment (i.e., where they can perceive many affordances), they are said to act intentionally (directed towards affordances). Intentionality continuously guides how the individual-environment system changes across time (i.e., its dynamics). Behavior, then, reflects ongoing adaptation to constraints, by means of coupled perception and action, in service of a task goal (Shaw, 2002; Tschacher & Haken, 2007). Returning to the notion

of complexity, mind and behavior under this view are not assumed to be confined to within an individual but rather result from the indivisibility of agent and environment towards a task goal.

While embodied cognition marks a significant shift from the standard approach by incorporating the body and its interactions with the environment, ecological dynamics goes further by rejecting internal representations altogether, as a means to explain perception and action (Raab & Araújo, 2019). This is reflected in its emphasis on the direct perception of affordances, making the environment not just a context for cognition but a constitutive element of it. In doing so, ecological dynamics embraces a more fundamental commitment to complexity, treating perception, action, and cognition as inseparable aspects of an adaptive complex system.

Consider, for example, Turvey's perceptual-motor synergies theory (Turvey, 1977, 1990, 2007; see also Bongers et al., 2025). Turvey, following Bernstein (1967), argued that the motor system has too many degrees of freedom for a central controller to manage each individually. Degrees of freedom are the possible states of individual components of a system that contribute to an overall movement, such as a joint. Specifically, the *degrees of freedom problem* states that every movement is such an exceedingly precarious interplay between many degrees of freedom that it is intractable to engage in controlling movement in a top-down fashion. Furthermore, the *problem of non-univocality* in commands (influences, instructions or constraints coming from upper levels of movement organization) state that the same motor command can yield different movements, and vice-versa, the same movements can correspond to different motor commands, depending on environmental changes (e.g., gravitational direction). These constitute a challenge to the dominant, centralized, view because such factors are not immediately accessible to a central controller, and it is intractable to transform these into the fine-grained changes in movement (Bernstein, 1967; Bongaardt & Meijer, 2000; Bongers et al., 2025). To resolve this, Turvey instead argued that the control and coordination of movement is governed by decentralized *synergies*. A synergy is a functional grouping of elements, temporarily coordinated as a single unit for specific tasks. Specifically, they act semi-autonomously, responding to perturbations by tension among components that maintains integrity, rather than

centralized commands. The control of movement therefore does not rely on top-down control but on the self-organization of the components implied in a particular movement. In a synergy, degrees of freedom of the elements regulate each other. This simplifies control of movement by reducing the number of independent elements that a central controller might need to manage. The soft-assembly tensegrity system temporarily acts as a single unit, solving the degrees of freedom problem for a certain task (see Bongers et al., 2025; and also Meijer & Roth, 1988).

Turvey further integrated the concept of synergies with Gibson's theory of perceptual information and affordances (Gibson, 1979). He extended this concept beyond the limited domain of muscle activation to situated action, or the coordination of the agent-environment system. In place of individual components self-organizing to perform an action, here it is components of the agent (including mental, emotional, kinematic, physiological, etc. components), task, and environment that form synergies. More precisely, they form perception-action couplings that guide perceptual-motor synergies (Kelso, 1995; Kugler & Turvey, 1987). Perceptual information specifies the formation of synergies and the control of movement is effectively the coordination of perception and action. Here, again, a central controller is replaced by self-organization. Importantly, rather than the agent being in control of the environment, subsystems of both the agent and the environment lawfully and reciprocally constrain each others' degrees of freedom, resulting in effective behavior (Profeta & Turvey, 2018).

Ecological dynamics' theories, as depicted in the example here, therefore rely on very different explanations from embodied cognition or the standard approach. In this view, behavior arises from the interactions among system components, while simultaneously shaping those components. This *circular causality* (Haken, 1977) is in stark contrast to the linear causality (of standard and embodied approaches), in which one component causes a change in one or few others, of standard approaches.

Ecological dynamics' departure from the standard approach is also reflected in its methods. A central theme in its methodology centers around Brunswik's (1955) representative design (Araújo et al., 2020). Aligned with the theoretical emphasis on environment-agent system, the representative design

approach avoids universal rules for validity in experimental design, instead demanding an analysis of a situation which evinces the central (to theory) relations between individual and situation that must be retained in the experimental setting (e.g., Araújo et al., 2005). Beyond representative experimental designs, ecological dynamics adopts a distinct set of variables – called eco-physical variables (Lopes et al., 2025) – which are grounded in the physical interaction between the individual and the environment, rather than on mental constructs (Araújo et al., 2020). These eco-physical variables capture how individuals regulate their actions to maintain a goal-directed trajectory, or goal-path, within a dynamic environment. Furthermore, these are substrate-independent and thereby manage to bridge mental and environmental components of behavioral phenomena.

For example, in a study of decision-making in boxing, Chow et al (2009), in place of looking to self-reported variables in order to predict a boxer's decision to change foot stance from a parallel to a (forward-leaning) diagonal stance, decided to use the distance between a boxer's toe and the opponent, scaled by the length of their arm, as the independent eco-physical variable. This eco-physical dependent variable demonstrates the ecological dynamics' assumption of interaction-dominance, in which one system cannot be understood by isolating the components which compose it. Rather, the relations (in this case measured by a body-scaled distance) are the units of interest. In relation to embodied cognition's methodological approach, there are also similarities. For example, embodied cognition acknowledges the importance of interactions between components of the brain-body-environment system, which drives its calls for naturalistic experiments. Yet, whereas, for the sake of explanation, embodied cognition decomposes a system of interest in its theories, ecological dynamics rejects this approach.

Nuancing Embodied Cognition and Ecological Dynamics

These descriptions should evince a picture in which embodied cognition and ecological dynamics both share some central assumptions which depart from standard approaches, while differing in others. They share the postulates that psychological phenomena should be understood as complex systems, yet they differ in their research strategies. While embodied cognition tends slightly

more towards a decomposition approach, ecological dynamics is fully committed to system-level research strategies.

Embodied cognition certainly takes a complexity assumption in the more metaphysical level. It rejects the very modular approach in which the cause of behavior is isolated to the brain, instead positing a complex interplay with reciprocal feedback loops. It also, as reflected in its demand for naturalistic designs, emphasizes that psychological processes emerge from interactions at scales. Nonetheless, the complexity assumptions are less strong in the third step, its research strategies. These align with reductionism. Its theories tend to aim for understanding isolated variables or phases (see the situated action cycle above). Although it acknowledges that these variables are in interaction, it nonetheless attempts to understand the system by understanding its components. Furthermore, its experiments, despite emphasizing naturalistic behavior, have the goal of identifying the characteristics of these single variables, and localizing these to specific regions.

Ecological dynamics assumes that psychological phenomena should be understood as complex systems, that they function, like other natural phenomena, as a complex system, and – in contrast to embodied cognition – that they should be investigated as a complex system. Ecological dynamics theories emphasize agent-environment system-level relations as primary explanatory constructs. Furthermore, its experimental methods go even further. On the one hand, they take more seriously the desire for ecological realism with the Brunswikian approach, reflecting the actual functional relations of the phenomenon under investigation. On the other hand, the variables are chosen to reflect relations as opposed to reflect the functioning of components, which manages to capture more of the complexity.

From Metaphysics to Theory

So much has been written about the (in)existence and (un)importance of mental representations (e.g., Brooks, 1991; Hutto & Myin, 2012; Raab & Araújo, 2019; Ramsey, 2007), that they have been termed the ‘representation wars’⁵. We will not aim to provide a comprehensive overview of, nor an answer to, this

⁵ We will not repeat the arguments here and instead refer the interested reader (or non-familiar) to the here-mentioned texts.

controversy here, but want to shortly nuance this discussion using the complexity view across levels of analysis. What is the reason for the rejection or acceptance of mental representations specifically? One may argue on epistemological grounds that this isolated component of mental representation is uninteresting because of the inseparability of agent and environment, or one may argue on theoretical grounds that they do not exist, irrespective of how one would investigate them.

As described above, embodied cognition, despite acknowledging the importance of the body, maintains that representations, or internal mental states⁶ exist and functionally contribute to mind and behavior. Theorists in ecological dynamics do not assume the existence of any such representations is needed. Yet, it is important to nuance these positions. The embodied cognition approach acknowledges the importance of brain-body-environment interaction in producing behavior. It therefore does not, as the standard approach, postulate the brain as a central controller, or locate causes to the brain exclusively. In fact, embodied cognition researchers can, and have, even taken the position that the overwhelming proportion of performance behavior is not driven by internal mediators (i.e., mental representations) but rather by direct contact with the environment (e.g., Clark, 2015). Such an acknowledgement of performer-environment coupling does not preclude the existence of mental representations though: A system can be coupled to another irrespective of whether it also has interesting, important internal states such as mental representations. Therefore, embodied cognition does not argue that mental content is the sole causal factor of behavior, and therefore does not violate assumptions about complexity, and is monist. This suggests that complexity does not necessarily require a theoretical rejection of mental states, but perhaps an epistemological.

⁶ We take the notion of mental representations to generally mean internal states which are separable from current sensory input which stand in for something else (Grush, 1997; Newen & Vosgerau, 2020). That means the term mental representations should not be taken to mean symbolic representations or algorithmic, digital computations (Maley, 2024).

Ecological dynamics' resistance to mental representations is driven by its system-level research-strategy, as well as by its assumed monist attributes of psychological phenomena⁷

The majority of psychological research, including the standard approach and embodied cognition research, typically takes as one of its central variables of investigation, mentally represented variables. Furthermore, just as embodied cognition, ecological dynamics argues that that psychology must be studied both scientifically rigorously and reflecting human experience. Yet, there is tension between these internal states and rigorous investigation. First, psychological phenomena rely on self-reports (e.g., level of motivation), which lack measurable precision. Ecological dynamics' alternative has often been the alternative, eco-physical descriptions (e.g., player-ball-goal angle). This way, psychology links physics of the world with biology of the body, captured by variables with psychological meaning (e.g., approaching or avoiding the target area; Shaw, 2001). Second, the attempt to explain or investigate mental representations requires research strategies which decompose to some degree, thereby violating the complexity assumption in the third step. In other words, it would attempt to isolate from the performer-environment system the mental states. This, according to a complexity metaphysics, is difficult or impossible, without misunderstanding or misrepresenting the nature of the phenomenon under investigation itself. This points to ecological dynamics' resistance to mental representations being motivated on the research strategy level.

⁷ Yet, it is important to distinguish between different versions of monism. While monism states that mental and natural phenomena are made of fundamentally the same 'stuff', it is still necessary to ask what this stuff is. Embodied cognition has the stance that the physical world is fundamental and mind is made of the same (physicalism). Ecological dynamics on the other hand, in line with James' radical empiricism, argues that what is primary is neither purely mental or purely physical, but rather something that links both (cf. James, 1904; Russell, 1927). This has the consequence that what is being experienced is different – the world or the mind. In the physicalism of embodied cognition, it is the mental representation which is apprehended, as a channel for the true environment, which is not the case of ecological dynamics', and especially Gibson's, direct perception. For Gibson information is specification, not representation, therefore ecological information is not some third thing between the agent and the object, it is, rather, the specificational relationship itself.

Adherence to complexity in research strategies does not by necessity imply a rejection of mental representations or internal knowledge structures. On the other hand, if motivated on the level of attributes (and by its monist stance), one may reject them also on more theoretic grounds. Ecological dynamics views psychological phenomena as emerging from agent–environment interactions. In this view, the environment is inherently meaningful and value-laden (thereby understanding the psychological phenomena as linking internal and external) and psychological experiences are grounded in the reciprocity between skills and affordance (Gibson, 1979; Turvey, 2019). On this view, with psychological experiences being expressed in the relationship between the person and the environment, there is no need to measure mediating mental states or even postulate them.

While the predominant position in ecological dynamics, in line with a systems-level research strategy, is not to postulate mental representations (e.g., Chemero, 2009) other related approaches do posit internal states as relevant. We shortly describe two. The theory of *ecological resonance* (Raja, 2018; Raja & Gramann, 2025) aligns with the assumption that behavior emerges from the self-organization of person and environment. Yet, it critically also views internal neurophysiological patterns as interesting and warranting explanation. This neural functioning is not assumed to be performing information processing (as under most mental-representational based approaches), but rather as resonating with the environment. Already Gibson (1966) proposed that the nervous system resonates to information. Metaphorically, he explained that many frequencies reach a radio receiver from the antenna, but proper tuning of the receiver causes an electric current in it to resonate according to some incoming signals, and not others. This means that, for vision, some ambient light patterns (information) specifying the environment can be detected by sensory receptors and corresponding nervous apparatus which must be tuned in to the information. The resonance apparatus resonates to information presenting affordances, aligning with ecological psychology's notion of direct perception. Resonance is not an accomplishment of the nervous system but involves all the body when perceiving and acting in the environment (Teques et al., 2017). This ecologically-steeped theory therefore aligns fully,

across all steps, with complexity, while nonetheless making room for interesting internal states.

A second approach is steeped in another central difference between systems-level and decomposition research: time (or a system's dynamics). In standard psychology, it is common practice to have cross-sectional designs, such as experimental designs with participants performing single actions that are repeated multiple times and treated as independent events (Vallacher et al., 2015; see also e.g., Berger et al., 2024; Wilt & Revelle, 2023; Miller, 2023). This is necessary in order to arrive at valid and reliable measurements of the isolated component under investigation. Embodied cognition is slightly less ignorant of time, but is still often satisfied with e.g., cross-sectional experiments that do not take the measurement dependencies into account. Ecological dynamics, as the name and its historical origins in dynamical systems literature reveals, takes the time-dependent component of phenomena very seriously, as also seen in its data analysis emphasizing time series' dependencies, autocorrelations, or fractal analyses (Riley & Van Orden, 2005).

Another dynamical systems-inspired, yet nonetheless representational approach involves dynamical theories of mental representations. Dynamical theories allow to depict and understand continuous variables, and have been applied as models of mental representations (Shapiro, 2013; Spivey, 2008). Here, unlike in standard approaches and embodied cognition (e.g., Barsalou, 1999; Quilty-Dunn et al., 2022), mental representations are not conceptualized as discrete states. Rather, a continuous state space landscape forms the space of possible mental states, and cognitive states are points moving continuously across this landscape. Deeper 'basins' are attractors, states which are revisited more frequently and readily. This approach similarly retains the notion of mental representations as internal states that mediate interaction with the environment. Yet, nonetheless managing to retain the complexity assumption throughout all three steps.

Conclusions

Concluding, we have emphasized the importance of considering metaphysical questions even for empirically minded researchers, and we have presented complexity as a valuable concept to structure these metaphysical topics. A complexity-guided navigation of metaphysical questions produces the

three steps concerning: 1) the origin, 2) the attributes, and 3) the research strategies of psychological phenomena. We also directed this tool towards ecological dynamics and embodied cognition, evincing a view in which both share central metaphysical positions, diverging in the application of these to methodological questions. Here, embodied cognition tends away from system-level towards the more traditional, decomposition, approach, while ecological dynamics is fully committed to systems-level decomposition.

Our intention is to encourage the interrogation of one's theories' and one's own metaphysical backdrop. Perhaps these questions and proposal may serve as a heuristic nudge, prodding colleagues, presenters, or corresponding authors in peer review toward further reflection.

Psychological science is occupied with the unenviable task of explaining a world which cannot be measured and if it could be explained, would contain far too many moving parts that could be put into writing. How to go about performing science in a way that explains it without misrepresentation is a considerable challenge. It is a challenge that requires the right tools, and complexity seems to be well suited for the job.

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